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Wnt control by Atg1611.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

In cells expressing IBD variant Atg1611, Wnt10b was induced, while Wnt5a was modestly repressed.

Citations

1. Bennett, C.N., Longo, K.A., Wright, W.S., Suva, L.J., Lane, T.F., Hankenson, K.D. and MacDougald, O.A., 2005. Regulation of osteoblastogenesis and bone mass by Wnt10b. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 102(9), pp.3324-3329.